

Dexarch v1.2.1 Installation Guide

Version: 1.2.1

Platform: Android

Minimum Android Version: 7.0 (Nougat) or higher

File Type: APK (Android Application Package)

Date: October 2025

Overview

Dexarch is a standalone Android application. This guide provides complete instructions for downloading, installing, and safely running the app on your Android device.

Note: Dexarch is verified and safe to install. The installation process requires a one-time permission to allow installation from unknown sources (outside Google Play).

Why We Are Providing the APK File

Dexarch is officially published on the Google Play Store. However, in certain situations, such as when:

- The app is temporarily unpublished for updates or policy compliance, or
- You are unable to find or access the app on the Play Store in your region, or
- There is a need to test or use the latest version before public release

You can safely install and test the application using the APK file provided on Zenodo. This APK file is the same version as the one published on the Google Play Store.

Handling Security Warnings & Installing

After you have downloaded the APK file from Zenodo or any other verified source, you need to click and install it. Depending on your device model and Android version, you may encounter messages such as:

- “This type of file can harm your device.”
- “For your security, your phone is not allowed to install unknown apps from this source.”

These are standard Android messages shown when installing apps manually (outside Play Store). To proceed safely, after tap on the APK file:

- Tap OK, Allow, or Install anyway when prompted.
- If installation is blocked:
 - Open Settings → Apps & Notifications → Special App Access → Install Unknown Apps.
 - Choose your browser or file manager (e.g., Chrome, Files).
 - Enable Allow from this source.
- Return to the download location, and tap the file to begin installation.
- Review any permission requests and tap Install again.
- Wait for the installation to complete (10–30 seconds).
- Once done, tap Open to launch Dexarch or Done to exit.

The app will now appear in your phone’s app drawer as Dexarch.

37 Security & Privacy Statement

- 38 • Dexarch v1.2.1 has been tested across multiple Android versions for safety and compatibility.
- 39 • Dexarch has no harmful code. It has been internally verified for safety, stability, and performance.
- 40 • The app does not collect, store, or transmit any personal data.
- 41 • Permissions requested are strictly necessary for app functionality.
- 42 • To the best of our knowledge, there are no known security or vulnerability issues associated with this
- 43 version.
- 44 • Refer to our privacy policy for more details: <https://reuben27.github.io/Dexarch-Privacy-Policy/>
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46 Support & Contact

47 For any help, technical issues, or feedback, please contact us at:

- 48 • reuben.shibu.devanesan@gmail.com
- 49 • kamalkvaishnav@gmail.com

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Thank you for installing Dexarch!
We appreciate your trust and hope you enjoy using the app.